

BM3D FRAMES WATERMARKING SCHEME IMAGES BASED ON THE FAST AND ADAPTIVE BI-DIMENSIONAL EMPIRICAL MODE DECOMPOSITION

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Abstract- We present a technique for the digital watermarking of still images based on FABEMD (Fast and Adaptive Bi-dimensional Empirical Mode Decomposition) where an additive watermarking scheme is applied to each BIMF (Bi-dimensional Intrinsic Mode Function) obtained by the FABEMD using the matrix of maxima of each BIMF and the special constraints for building the watermarking scheme in order to ensure the invisibility, the facility of detection of the mark and the robustness against different kinds of attacks. The use of the FABEMD in watermarking is motivated by the fact that it has better quality than another transform domain watermarking method in extracting intrinsic components because of its fully data driven property, and this decomposition is also proven as a very powerful tool for multi-scale analysis of non-stationary and non-linear signals and also by the characteristics of the BIMF. Simulation results show the superior performance of the technique and demonstrate its potential for the robust watermarking of imagery.

Keywords: Bi-dimensional Empirical Mode Decomposition, Bi dimensional Intrinsic Mode Functions, Fast and Adaptive Bi dimensional Empirical Mode Decomposition, Watermarking, Watermarking scheme, robustness, Watermark invisibility, Watermarking attacks, Robustness.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the increasing amount of digital data sharing tools due to the growth of the internet; thing that increased the availability of images to the internet users; frauds are multiplied which accentuated the need to find robust marking techniques for digital data protection. Researches prove that watermarking is a valid solution for such a need. Digital watermarking is the imperceptible marking of multimedia data to “brand” ownership. The process of digital watermarking involves the Modification of the original Multimedia data to embed a watermark containing key information Such as authentication or copyright codes. The embedding method must leave the original data perceptually unchanged, yet should impose Modifications which can be detected by using an appropriate extraction algorithm. Previous methods for Watermarking images can be placed under two categories based on whether or not they use the original image during the watermark detection process. Schemes reported in [1, 2, 3] require the original image for detection, where as the method in [4] does not. Most of the reported schemes use an additive watermark, the watermark being added to the image in the spatial domain [5, 6] or in the transform domain [1, 2, 3, 4, and 7]. It is found that the transform domain watermarking schemes are typically much more robust to image manipulation as compared to the spatial domain schemes. The proposed scheme does not use the original image for watermark detection and casts the watermark in a BIMF [8].

The basic idea of our method is to insert a different mark into the each Bi dimensional Intrinsic Mode Functions after decomposing the image by the BEMD or by FABEMD (Fast and Adaptive Bi dimensional Empirical Mode Decomposition) using the special constraints for building the watermarking scheme in order to ensure the invisibility, the facility of detection of the mark and the robustness

against different kinds of attacks. The BEMD is an extension of the EMD (Empirical Mode Decomposition) [9], which can decompose non-linear and non-stationary signals into basis functions called the Intrinsic Modes Functions (IMFs). IMFs are mono component functions that have well defined instantaneous frequencies. EMD is a sifting process that is non-parametric and data driven; it does not depend on a priori basis set. BEMD decomposes an image into two-dimension BIMFs; the process is called 2D sifting process. FABEMD is an approach for BEMD using an approach of Envelope estimation [10].

Extraction of each BIMF requires several iterations. Because the surface interpolation method itself fits a surface in an iterative optimization approach, it makes the BEMD process complex and excessively time consuming, so to overcome this problem we propose a FABEMD technique which shows greater robustness to common signal distortions. The Fundamental advantage of our FABEMD technique lies in the method used to embed the watermark in each BIMF. This scheme of insertion has the characteristic to provide a good Performance of detection of the mark against attacks because of the redundancy of the watermark in the watermarked image and we can Watermark an image for all dimensions in a very Short time. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: In the section (2), we introduce the BEMD and the FABEMD. Section (3) focuses on the proposed method for digital watermarking. The experimental results for different kinds of images are presented in the following section. Conclusions and future works are presented in the final section.

II. THE BI-DIMENSIONAL EMPIRICAL MODE DECOMPOSITION(BEMD)

The Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) is a relatively concept in the area of signal processing [9];it's locally adaptive and suitable for analysis of nonlinear and non-stationary processes. This decomposition technique extracts a finite number of oscillatory components or (well-behaved) AM-FM functions, directly from the data. IMFs are mono component functions that have well defined instantaneous frequencies. EMD does not use any pre-determined filter or basis functions; which is quite different from Gabor analysis [11] and Wavelet analysis [12]. This technique extended to analyse two-dimensional data is known as Bi dimensional EMD (BEMD). The procedure of decomposition is iterative. The 2D sifting process is performed in two steps: extrema detection by neighboring windows or morphological operators and surface interpolation by radial basis functions [13] or multigrid B-spline. Its principle is to decompose adaptively an image into its BIMFs.

A. THE BEMD STEPS

a. Algorithm

Given an image I , the 2D sifting process of BEMD can be defined as follows [8] (The diagram of the BEMD is presented in figure. 1):

- Step 1) Fixed. $\epsilon, i \leftarrow 1$
- Step 2) $r_{i-1} \leftarrow I$ (residue)
- Step 3) Extract the i^{th} BIMF:
 - a) $h_{i,j-1} \leftarrow r_{i-1}, j \leftarrow 1$ (j , iteration of the loop of shifting)
 - b) Extract local maxima and minima of $h_{i,j-1}$.
 - c) Compute upper envelope and lower envelope functions $U_{i,j-1}$ and $L_{i,j-1}$ by interpolating, respectively, local minima and local maxima of $h_{i,j-1}$.
 - d) Compute local mean surface:
 - e) Update: $h_{i,j} \leftarrow h_{i,j-1} - m_{i,j}, j \leftarrow j + 1$
 - f) Calculate stopping criterion:(Standard Deviation)
 - g) Repeat steps (b)-(f) until $SD(j) \leq \epsilon$, let

$$\text{BIMF}_i \leftarrow h_{i,j} \text{ (i}^{\text{eme}} \text{ BIMF)}.$$
- Step 4) Update residue: $r_i \leftarrow r_{i-1} - \text{BIMF}_i$

- Step 5) Repeat steps (3) with $i \leftarrow i + 1$ until the number of extrema in r_i is less than 2 i.e., The residue does not contain any extrema points.

The Standard Deviation (SD) is the criteria to stop sifting process, computed from two consecutive sifting (formula 1).

$$SD(j) = \sum_{i=1}^T \frac{|h_{i,j} - h_{i,j-1}|^2}{h_{i,j-1}^2} \quad (1)$$

T: the number of iterations.

The algorithm precedent described the diagram. When the decomposition is complete, the original image may be reconstructed by adding all the BIMFs and the last residue (formula 2).

$$I_{reconstructed} = \sum_{i=1}^k BIMF_i + Residue \quad (2)$$

Where k is the number of BIMFs.

Extraction of each BIMF requires several iterations. Because the surface interpolation method itself fits a surface in an iterative optimization approach, it makes the BEMD process complex and excessively time consuming, so to overcome this problem we can accelerate the process and minimize the computational time by the use of the New Bi dimensional Empirical Mode Decomposition (NBEMD) [14], Olympics Bi dimensional Empirical Mode Decomposition (OBEMD) [15], the Lapped Block Bi dimensional Empirical Mode Decomposition (LBBEMD) [16] and Fast and Adaptive Bi dimensional Empirical Mode Decomposition (FABEMD) [10]. In this work, we used the FABEMD for accelerate the watermarking.

Figure 1. The diagram of BEMD

B. Image extrema extraction

The first step of the sifting process in the BEMD is to locate the local extrema points (maxima and minima) of the image intensity. The simple way is to use the pixel neighbouring information in the image; so a point is maxima (respectively minima) if its value is strictly higher (respectively strictly lower) than all its 8-connected closer neighbours

C. Surface interpolation

The interpolation is regarded as a delicate stage in the sifting process and has a remarkable influence on the results of the decomposition. A natural extension for the interpolation method used in the EMD for one dimensional is the cubic spline interpolation for the bi dimensional signals. Unfortunately, this method decomposes the two dimensional down to residue with a many number of extrema points and it creates distortions near the end points. All this is because the data we have to interpolate is often described as scattered. Radial Basis Functions provide well-established tools for solving interpolation problems of the above form in any space dimension. An RBF is a function of the form:

$$s(x) = p_m(x) + \sum \lambda_i \Phi(\|x - x_i\|) \quad x \in \mathfrak{R}^d, \lambda_i \in \mathfrak{R} \quad (3)$$

Where s is the RBF, p_m is a low-degree polynomial, typically linear or quadratic, a member of the m^{th} degree polynomials in d variables, $\| \cdot \|$ denotes the Euclidean norm, The λ_i 's are the RBF coefficients, Φ is the basis function and x_i are the RBF centers. For this interpolation method we should fix in advance the basis function and since there are many functions that can be used as a basis function we can consider the Thin-Plate [9] as an extension of the cubic spline function as in the case of one dimension:

$$\Phi(r) = r^2 \log(r)$$

For the BEMD interpolation, the RBF offers several advantages over piece wise polynomial interpolates because the geometry of the known points is not restricted and the resulting system of linear equations is guaranteed to be invertible under very mild conditions.

D. . Stopping criteria for the 2D sifting process

The 2D sifting process in the BEMD decomposition consist on decomposing an input signal into set of functions defined by the signal itself, these functions are called IMFs. A BIMF is characterized by some specific properties [8, 18]: Each BIMF is expected to have the following properties

- The number of zero crossings and the number of extrema points is equal or differs by only one.
- The envelopes defined by the local maxima and minima, respectively, are locally symmetric around the envelope mean.

The 2D sifting process stops when the resulting image satisfied the characteristics of a BIMF, as it is described above. In other term, it stops when the envelope mean signal is close enough to zero. After a BIMF is found, we define the residue as the result of subtracting this BIMF from the input image and then we iterate on the residue. The BEMD is completed when the residue, ideally, does not contain any extrema points. This is if we suppose that the sifting process will converge, things that never been rigorously demonstrated. So, we have to determine a criterion for the sifting process to stop, this can be accomplished by limiting the size of the SD, computed from the two consecutive sifting results as: In practice, we have used SD between 0.02 and 0.3 and this stop criterion gives satisfying results.

E. Stopping criteria for the decomposition

Generally, the decomposition stops when the number of extrema is less than 2; that's mean that there is no more oscillations to extract. In some case we can have a high number of BIMFs without meeting this condition, so we should set a maximal number of BIMF to extract. We can stop. The decomposition depending on the need; for example, in image denoising we will need only the first BIMF [19] and in texture-image retrieval we will need all BIMFs [20].

III. WATERMARK EMBEDDING USING THE BEMD

As a first application of image watermarking using the IMF after decomposition by BEMD, we will use the "Patchwork" algorithm; proposed by Bender and Al.[Ben 95]. We will apply the additive watermarking scheme to each IMF obtained by the BEMD where the watermark is a binary matrix

in $\{-1, 1\}$ differently ponderated for each one of the four first IMF_i modes, $i=1 \dots 4$, and at the end watermarked image is reconstructed by adding all the watermarked IMF and the residue (Figure 1.). The watermark insertion scheme is as follow:

Step.1 Decompose the original image to the fourth first modes and residue:

$$I = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{IMF}_i + \text{residue} \quad \text{with } n=4$$

Step.2 for each IMF, using a secret private key to

Select randomly a sequence of n couples of pixels (A_i, B_i) in the IMF to be modified lightly in such a way to increase (or decrease) by a unit the intensity value of the pixels of the type A_i and to decrease (or increase) by a unit the intensity value of the pixels of the type B_i. In such way there will be a unique private key for each IMF.

Step.3 Embedding in each IMF the equivalent mark:

$$\text{IMF}_{w_i} = \text{IMF}_i + \alpha_i \times R_i \quad \text{with } i=1 \dots 4$$

and
$$R_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{If pixels are in } A_i \\ -1 & \text{If pixels are in } B_i \\ 0 & \text{Others} \end{cases}$$

IMF is the original intrinsic mode function,

IMF_w is the watermarked intrinsic mode function, α is a ponderation and R is the binary watermark matrix

Step.4 Building the watermarked image by adding all

the watermarked IMF and the residue of the decomposition of the original image by the BEMD:

$$I_w = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{IMF}_{w_i} + \text{residue} \quad \text{with } n=4$$

Figure 2. Diagram of watermark embedding method using BEMD

IV. WATERMARK DETECTION USING THE BEMD

The watermark detection is done by operation dual of the one used in image watermarking process (Figure.2.).The watermark detection scheme is as follow:

Step.1 Decompose the watermarked image to the fourth first modes and residue:

$$I_w = \sum_{i=1}^n \text{IMF}_{w_i} + \text{residue} \quad \text{with } n=4$$

Step.2 For each MF_w, and using the secret private

key;used in the referencing stage in the watermarking process; select the sequence of n couples pixels (A_i, B_i) in the MF_w to be modified lightly in such a way to increase (or decrease) by a unit the intensity value of the pixels of the type A_i and to decrease (or increase) by a unit the intensity value of the pixels of the type B_i .

Step.3 Extraction of the watermark from each IMF:

$$IMF_i^* = IMF_{w_i} + \alpha_i \times R_i \text{ with } i = 1 \dots 4$$

$$\text{and } R_i = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{If pixels are in } A_i \\ 1 & \text{If pixels are in } B_i \\ 0 & \text{Others} \end{cases}$$

IMF_w is the watermarked intrinsic mode function, IMF^* is the intrinsic mode function after extracting the watermark, α is a ponderation and R is the binary watermark matrix

Step.4 Verifying the existence of the watermark by a threshold on the result of correlation between each IMF_i^* and IMF_i and between the original image and the image after extraction of the watermark

Figure 3. Diagram of watermark detection method using BEMD

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

5.1 Watermark Embedding and Detection Without Attacks

A first application is to test our method for a gray scale image (Lena) of 512 x 512 and try to extract the watermark without any attack on the watermarked image.

5.1.1 Embedding

Figure 4. Watermark embedding: a) Original image, b) Watermarked image, c) difference between original image and watermarked image.

In Figure.4. We presented in a) the image before insertion of the watermark (original image), in b) the watermarked image is presented to show the invisibility of the watermark in the watermarked image and at the end in c) the difference (the watermark) between the original image and the watermarked image is presented.

It is clear that the first characteristic of a watermarking method which is the invisibility of the watermark is respected in our method.

5.1.2 Detection

We presented in Figure.5. the results of the detection of the watermark in the watermarked image. So, to verify the existence of the mark in the watermarked image, a measure of correlation between the watermarked image after extraction of the watermark and the original image is done.

Figure 5. Detection of the existence of the watermark without any attack: a) Watermarked image, b) image after extraction of the watermark, c) correlation between the watermarked image after extraction of the Watermark and the original image as well as the correlation between the modes (IMF). If there are no attacks the detection of the watermark is done without any problem.

5.2 Robustness of the Method Against Attacks

Certainly once watermarked images are diffused in the internet can be victims of attacks and arbitrary transformed. If these attacks do not much degrade the watermarked image, a robust watermarking method should detect the watermark as long as the watermarked image quality is not rendered useless. So, to test the robustness of our method against attacks, we will present some examples of attacks/detection.

5.2.1 Robustness Against White Noise Attack

We can suppose that for image with moderate signal-to-noise ratio, the noise is of lower amplitude than the extrema points. We will apply to the watermarked image a Gaussian white additive noise with zero mean. We can suppose that for image with moderate signal-to-noise ratio, the noise is of lower amplitude than the extrema points. So, after decomposing the watermarked image, we can reduce the noise by setting the extrema points with low amplitude to zero in the first IMF; the remaining values represent only significant extrema points. That means that the problem of noise attacks on the watermarked images could be treated at the level of the first mode without influencing a lot the other modes.

Figure 6. a) Watermarked Image with white noise, b) Watermarked image after reducing the noise, c) correlation between the watermarked image after extraction of the watermark and the original image as well as the correlation between the modes (IMF).

The correlation results show that the attack by the white noise has been felt on the first IMF and did not have big impacts on the other modes. Thus, we can say that our method is robust against an attack of against white noise.

5.2.2 Robustness Against JPEG Compression Attack

Image compression consists in transmitting only the significant components, and since the watermark is invisible in the watermarked image it will be seen in the compression process as non useful

information. To remedy this problem Cox and al [Cox 97] proposed to insert the watermark in significant places in the image. The idea to make our method robust to the JPEG compression is to modify the DCT coefficients [Koc 95] of each IMF in the JPEG process as follow:

- Split Each IMF into non-overlapping 8x8 blocks.
- Take the two-dimensional DCT of each block.
- Scanning the DCT component matrix in zigzag pattern to keep only significant components located in the upper left corner.
- Finally, the modifications are done on the low frequency coefficient quantified triplet. In this way we are sure that the watermark will be not removed form the image and also it will be invisible.

The existence of the watermark is checked by comparing the original image and the decompressed image watermarked image after extracting the watermark

Figure 7 . a) Watermarked image JPEG compressed using quality 50%, b) Image after watermark extraction, c) Correlation between the two images.

In Figure.7. We presented the watermarked image with quality factor equal to 50%, the image after extracting the watermark and the correlation between the two images and the IMF. The correlation results show that the watermark exists in the watermarked image after JPEG compression and decompression. To evaluate our method for different JPEG quality factor, we tested to verify the existence of the watermark in the JPEG compressed watermarked image with different quality factor. Table 1. Presents the results of correlation for different JPEG quality factor.

TABLE I
CORRELATION RESULTS FOR DIFFERENT JPEG QUALITY FACTOR (%)

JPEG quality	Correlation
8	0.5460
40	0.7890
60	0.9968
80	0.9992
100	1

The results obtained are very encouraging in terms of visual; the PSNR equal to 39.50dB; and also the correlation result between the compressed image after watermark extraction and the original image is very encouraging.

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In this paper we presented a new image watermarking based on the BEMD decomposition. This method presents an important asset because of the redundancy of the watermark in the watermarked image (four different watermark are present in the watermarked image), thing which gives us four times more robustness with respect to the methods aiming to extract the watermark. Although, we did not present the robustness of the method with respect to all the attacks but seen the results presented here our method presents an excellent behavior against noise and JPEG compressions attacks which lets us say that it is very promising images watermarking method.

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